

Table 1. Effect of variation of reactants concentrations on the reaction rate at 35 °C

$[\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2] = 1.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}] = 5.72 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (dextrose), $1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (maltose), $[\text{S}] = \text{Substrate}$

$[\text{IO}_4^-] \times 10^3$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{S}] \times 10^3$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{KCl}] \times 10^3$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$(-dc/dt) \times 10^7$ (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹) (dextrose)	$(-dc/dt) \times 10^7$ (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹) (maltose)
0.83	5.00	1.00	1.53	1.60
1.00	5.00	1.00	1.71	1.66
1.25	5.00	1.00	2.00	2.20
1.67	5.00	1.00	2.66	2.80
2.50	5.00	1.00	4.00	4.00
5.00	5.00	1.00	7.40	7.60
1.00	1.66	1.00	1.50	1.48
1.00	2.00	1.00	1.40	1.54
1.00	2.50	1.00	1.55	1.53
1.00	3.33	1.00	1.60	1.42
1.00	5.00	1.00	1.71	1.66
1.00	10.00	1.00	1.71	1.66
1.00	5.00	0.83	1.71	1.60
1.00	5.00	1.00	1.71	1.66
1.00	5.00	1.25	1.90	1.77
1.00	5.00	1.67	1.81	1.77
1.00	5.00	2.50	2.00	1.60
1.00	5.00	5.00	2.00	1.50

Table 2. Effect of variation of mercuric acetate, perchloric acid and ionic strength (μ) at 35 °C

$[\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}] = 5.72 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{NaIO}_4] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{KCl}] = 1.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{S}] = 5.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, dex./mal. = dextrose and maltose

$[\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2] \times 10^3$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{HClO}_4] \times 10^3$ (mol dm ⁻³) dex./mal.	$[\mu] \times 10^3$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$(-dc/dt) \times 10^7$ (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹) (dextrose)	$(-dc/dt) \times 10^7$ (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹) (maltose)
0.83	2.50/1.00	-	1.40	1.40
1.00	2.50/1.00	-	1.42	1.71
1.25	2.50/1.00	-	1.71	1.66
1.67	2.50/1.00	-	1.50	1.68
2.50	2.50/1.00	-	1.55	1.48
5.00	2.50/1.00	-	1.65	1.54
1.25	0.83/0.83	-	1.55	1.50
1.25	1.00/1.00	-	1.45	1.66
1.25	1.25/1.25	-	1.42	1.66
1.25	1.67/1.67	-	1.50	1.68
1.25	2.50/2.50	-	1.71	1.70
1.25	5.00/5.00	-	1.50	1.60
1.25	2.50/1.00	0.83	1.71	1.60
1.25	2.50/1.00	1.00	1.66	1.64
1.25	2.50/1.00	1.25	1.64	1.58
1.25	2.50/1.00	1.67	1.71	1.66
1.25	2.50/1.00	2.50	1.68	1.60
1.25	2.50/1.00	5.00	1.71	1.60

ionic strength of the medium on the rate, and the reaction is unaffected by hydrogen ion concentration (Table 2). The kinetic studies were also made in the 30–45 °C range and specific rate constants obtained were used to draw a plot between $\log k_r$ versus $1/T$ which was linear from which the activation parameters were calculated (Table 3).

Table 3. Activation parameters for oxidation of dextrose and maltose

Parameters	Temp. (°C)	Dextrose	Maltose
$k_r \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)	30	1.14	1.10
$k_r \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)	35	1.71	1.66
$k_r \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)	40	2.45	2.42
$k_r \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)	45	3.46	3.48
$\log A$	–	10.29	11.81
ΔE^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	–	59.34	68.37
ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	35	75.31	75.38
ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	35	71.50	73.71
ΔS^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	35	-12.35	-5.42

The results of oxidation of dextrose and maltose show that, the reactions follow identical kinetics and thus appear to have a common mechanism. The following reaction steps are suggested on the basis of the above discussion for oxidation of dextrose and maltose by sodium periodate in presence of rhodium(III) chloride as a catalyst.

[P] = Gluconic acid and maltobionic acid for dextrose and maltose respectively. Considering the above reaction steps and applying the steady state treatment with reasonable approximation, the rate law may be written as :

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 [\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}] [\text{HIO}_4]$$

From the present investigation it is concluded that, rhodium-tri-chloride as such is the reactive species of the catalyst in acidic medium.

References

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